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Title

Contextual factors influencing intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP) uptake

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Contextual Factors Influencing IPTp-SP Uptake

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Introduction

The World Health Organization recommends intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in pregnancy (IPTp) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) for all pregnant women in areas with moderate to high malaria transmission, including most sub-Saharan African countries. Despite implementation of the policy for over a decade, coverage of IPTp-SP remains low, with only 32% of women in sub-Saharan Africa receiving the recommended 3 or more doses.¹ Many studies have been performed assessing a variety of contextual factors that could contribute to treatment uptake. These contextual factors include acceptability, feasibility, operational considerations, costing, and equity/health equality. Given low uptake, it is important to understand the contextual factors surrounding IPTp-SP and how they might be influence uptake.

A prior systematic review of the barriers and facilitators of IPTp uptake was published in 2013,² and found a number of barriers, which were largely consistent across countries, and which were categorized as pertaining to the pregnant woman (including knowledge, gender roles, societal & cultural norms, physical access/transportation, and user fees, to name a few), the provider (knowledge, confusing/ contradictory guidance), or the health system (staff management/ workload, availability of drugs, clean water). However, as IPTp-SP uptake has increased substantially since then (it was only 8% in 2013)³, we reviewed the contextual information by summarizing the results from studies with relevant information identified using the search for studies with IPTp-SP data from March 2018-September 2021.

Methods

Electronic database searches

The assessment of contextual factors was conducted alongside a quantitative review which comprised an update to a previously published review by van Eijk, et al.⁴ We searched PubMed/MEDLINE (OVID), EMBASE (OVID), Global Health (OVID), Cochrane Library, CINAHL (EbscoHost), Scopus, the Malaria in Pregnancy library (<https://mip.wwarn.org/index.php?records&m=search&page=1&ipp=100>), and the conference proceedings from the ASTMH 69th Annual Meeting (November 2020) using the search terms: “Malaria AND pregnan* AND intermittent AND (prevent* OR prophyla* OR chemoprevent* OR chemoprophyla* OR IPT*) AND (sulfadoxine OR sulphadoxine OR pyrimethamine OR SP)” from March

2018 onwards, with no language restrictions. In addition, because the prior review excluded studies without a zero-dose group, we used the same search strategy, restricted to clinical trials only, without time period restrictions. The last update to the search was performed September 9, 2021.

Two people (JG, AvE) performed the initial screen and tagged articles with possible information on acceptability, feasibility, operational considerations, costing, adherence to treatment, and equity, without regard for study design. Two people (ER, JA) individually reviewed all tagged articles and abstracted data on these contextual factors into a standardized form. These were then collated and reviewed for consistency, any discrepancies resolved by either discussion/ consensus or involvement of a third reviewer (JG), and data were summarized by topic: Acceptance, Operational and Feasibility Considerations, Resource and Economic Considerations, and Health Equity/ Equality.

Results

Following deduplication of the initial list in endnote (n= 1036), a total of 867 references were identified. Among 488 excluded from the qualitative analysis by title/abstract screening, 36 were identified for inclusion in the contextual factor review. Among 379 full text studies reviewed for the qualitative review, 40 were identified for inclusion in the contextual factor review, for a total of 76 studies included in the contextual factor summary (eight of these were also included in the quantitative analysis; Table 1).

Acceptance

Knowledge of IPTp-SP of both healthcare workers and patients play a role in IPTp-SP uptake. With regard to patient knowledge, one study in Nigeria found that women who were aware of the proper number of doses of IPTp-SP needed were 4.70 times more likely to accept and adhere to the treatment; women who participated in information sessions on IPTp-SP at ANC had 4.61-fold higher uptake of IPTp-SP.⁵ Similarly, many studies reported that women's knowledge of IPT-SP was associated with higher acceptance and increased uptake.⁶⁻²⁴ A qualitative study in Malawi found that women who reported positive attitudes towards IPTp were more likely to receive optimal doses (41.4% vs 12.7%, $p < 0.0001$).²⁵

ANC attendance appears to be a main driver influencing patient acceptance of IPTp-SP. Numerous studies reported increased uptake of IPTp-SP with early initiation of education and counselling sessions at ANC, specifically during the first-trimester, as well as frequent ANC visits.^{6,7,9-12,15,17,20,22,26-46} Among these studies, adherence to at least one dose of IPTp-SP was reported between 70-98%. A qualitative analysis across four sub-Saharan countries found that it is crucial to build a trusting relationship between community healthcare workers and women in the community to enhance IPTp acceptability.⁴⁷ A study in Uganda found 89.6% acceptability of IPTp by women through community-based IPTp intervention.⁴⁸ Overall, acceptance of IPTp-SP by pregnant women is high, and is improved further through communication and education.

Adverse effects of SP and acceptance

In general, women who were concerned about the side effects of SP were less likely to take the recommended number of doses of IPTp-SP. In a 2019 study conducted in Ghana, women who stated that there are no side effects were more likely to take the optimal number of doses of IPTp-SP than women who indicated concern about the safety or the side effects of the treatment.¹¹ Similarly, a participatory study conducted across three African countries (Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria, and Mozambique) found that negative perceptions of SP and its side effects reduced adequate dose uptake by women.⁴⁹ However, neither an individually randomized longitudinal trial in Malawi nor a cross sectional study of third trimester pregnant women (interviewed at ≥ 36 weeks) in Ghana found that the actual occurrence of adverse events (AEs) following IPTp administration reduced IPTp adherence.^{28,50} A study including 12 midwives in private facilities in Ghana found that the midwives general knowledge of IPTp-SP guidelines was low, but all 12 were able to state common side effects of SP.²⁸

Operational and Feasibility Considerations

Twenty-one studies assessed operational and feasibility considerations associated with IPTp administration. Intermittent stock-outs were noted by thirteen studies as a common barrier to improving IPTp-SP uptake.^{7,10,16,19,24,37,39,49,51-55} In Western Kenya, SP accounted for 28% of all antimalarial drugs available in government-controlled health facilities, however, the hospitals and health center pharmacies still reported overall stock shortages of SP.⁵⁴ Many studies reported similar SP availability issues within government-run health facilities and wards.^{7,10,19,24,37,49,51-53} A study conducted in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania found that SP was readily available in 67% of community medicine outlets.⁵⁶

Several studies found that both stock shortages and inadequate prescriptions by health care workers (< 3 doses of SP) contributed to inadequate uptake.^{10,16,39,53,55} Inadequate staffing may contribute to poor uptake; in a study in Mozambique, nurses stated that a main barrier to IPTp-SP effectiveness and efficiency is the high patient load.⁵⁷

Limited knowledge and training of the staff on the prevention and management of malaria in pregnancy, including indications for IPTp-SP, contribute to poor uptake.^{34,53,56,58,59} Some healthcare workers expressed concerns regarding the lack of ongoing training in updating their knowledge.⁵³ This is country and site dependent, as a study in Ghana found that all twelve of the interviewed healthcare workers demonstrated adequate knowledge about malaria and IPTp.⁶ In Cameroon, among 39 healthcare workers, while all providers understood the importance of IPTp-SP, 28% and 41% did not know when to start and stop IPTp-SP, and 36% received not having received any training on IPTp.⁵¹ In this study, about 10% of the providers who identified themselves as “nurses” had no formal training in nursing practice.⁵¹

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that IPTp-SP be administered by directly observed therapy (DOT) to ensure administration of IPTp-SP; DOT is generally, but not always, associated with improved uptake of IPTp-SP.^{25,51,60} Utilization of DOT was variable,^{6,7} with between 5-67% of pregnant women reporting taking IPT-SP under DOT.^{51,61-63} In Cameroon, Diengou et al reported that 85% of providers practice the policy of DOT.⁵¹ In a multi-site study in Ghana, SP was given as DOT at all of the study sites.²⁴ However, another study in Ghana found that DOT was not strictly enforced, and women who preferred to take the drug home were allowed to do so.²⁷ In a 2020 study conducted in Abuja, Nigeria, none of the eight included clinics actively practiced DOT.⁵³ Reasons for not providing DOT included lack of water and cups as well as the preference of women to take SP at home after meals.⁵¹

Resource and Economic Considerations

Among eight facilities in Abuja, Nigeria, in 2018, all facilities reported that IPTP-SP was readily available the majority of the time, but all noted that it was sometimes necessary to procure drugs from the private sector or borrow from another government facility.⁵³ Stock shortages were noted to be an occasional issue which would result in pregnant women being issued a prescription to buy SP from a private facility; this occurred with enough frequency that all eight interviewed healthcare workers suggested that improvements in SP availability would be helpful.⁵³ Additional barriers noted in this study and others were long waiting times, lack of health worker training and education resources, and inconvenient facility locations.^{21,53,57,59}

Many studies reported data on the use of insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs) by pregnant women. ITN use reported within these studies ranged between 25% and 50%.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁸ One study in Ibadan, Nigeria, 2019, reported that while 49.9% of women utilized ITNs, and 27.9% took IPTp, only 15% of pregnant women complied with both interventions.⁶⁵

A major contributor to utilization of antenatal care (ANC) and malaria prevention resources was affordability. Women who could not afford general maternal healthcare were found to skip or delay ANC and decline recommended laboratory tests.^{52,69} In another study, which includes synthesized data from several trials performed in Sub-Saharan Africa (Burkina Faso, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Tanzania, and Zambia), the total household cost per ANC visit was reported at about \$1.64, including the direct and indirect costs of transportation; 25% was attributed to IPTp-SP.⁷⁰

Based on data collected during an individually randomized, placebo controlled trial in Mozambique conducted 2003-2005,⁷¹ Sicuri et al. found IPTp-SP to be a highly cost-effective intervention. The intervention cost of delivering two doses of IPTp-SP to 1000 pregnant women through ANC was about USD435.79, with a net intervention cost of USD13.17.⁷² Delivering two doses of IPTp-SP to 1000 pregnant women resulted in a total health system cost savings of USD422.74, 43% of which was attributed to reduced hospital admissions.⁷² IPTp-SP led to substantial household cost-savings for women seen in the outpatient department (33.89 US\$ (CI 95% 6.10, 77.20) in direct costs and 83.79 US\$ (CI 95% 29.60, 148.30) in indirect costs), but did not lead to a statistically significant household cost saving for women who required admission for malaria (8.20 US\$ (CI 95% -42.80, 55.80) in direct

costs and 11.44 US\$ (CI 95% –20.50, 42.70) in indirect costs). It was estimated that delivering IPTp-SP to 1000 pregnant women would avert 18.93 (CI 95% 4.39, 33.85) neonatal deaths, or 555.21 (CI 95% 129.00, 992.00) DALYs.⁷² This study found that IPTp-SP is no longer cost-effective when ANC attendance is lower than 37.5%, the protective efficacy of IPTp-SP against maternal infection is lower than 15%, malaria incidence is lower than 0.15 person-year at risk, or case fatality rate is lower than 0.15%.⁷²

Based on the data from Mozambique, the intervention costs of delivering two doses of IPTp-SP were USD41.46 per DALYs averted,⁷² while an analysis of three vs two doses of IPTp-SP found that IPTp-SP3+ was \$7.28 per DALY averted.⁷⁰ The cost of one dose of IPTp-SP was reported between USD0.63 and USD0.79.^{70,73}

While it is policy to provide IPTp-SP free of charge in many countries, in at least some places, because the costs of providing the care fall to the facilities, facilities may charge for SP, lab tests, or consultations, such that ANC is no longer free, as noted in Ghana.⁵² Even when women have insurance, many women paid out-of-pocket for at least half of the cost of ANC services, and when uninsured, they were forced to pay the full cost of some services, though some services remained free.⁵² Similarly, in a Nigerian study it was noted that whether women were charged for SP depended on whether it had been procured by the facility or supplied by the area council.⁵³ Thus, not only may women be asked to pay for SP and other ANC services, but these costs may not be consistent at each visit. The costs for services may lead women to present for ANC late (to reduce the total visits during pregnancy) or to decline services that they cannot afford.⁵²

Cost of Treatment for Malaria

A Nigerian study estimated that with 56.5% uptake of at least one dose of IPTp in pregnant women, the cost of treatment of malaria in pregnancy- primarily with artemisinin-based combination therapy- is about USD78.6 million, translating to about 0.016% of the Nigerian gross domestic product (GDP).⁷⁴ The mean cost of treatment for malaria during pregnancy in this study was USD11.86, roughly evenly split between consultation, laboratory, and drug costs, and administration fees, and a smaller proportion arising from transportation costs.⁷⁴ This study noted that essentially all the payments for treatment of malaria in pregnancy are out-of-pocket, thus, to the extent that providing IPTp-SP can prevent the need for treatment, it confers substantial savings to women and their families.

Health Equity

Age, marital status, religion, and living in a rural area were found by many studies to influence the inequality of opportunity for IPTp uptake.^{9,11,26,31,32,41-43,45,68,75-77} Women under 20 years were generally the least likely to receive 3 doses of IPTp-SP, with those between 25-34 most likely to receive IPTp-SP.^{41,42,60,78,79} A large multicountry analysis of malaria indicator datasets found that women between 20-34 were more likely to have received at least 3 doses of IPTp-SP than younger or older women:

women aged 25-29 were the most likely to receive 3 doses.⁷⁷ A couple of studies reported that being older than 30 years of age was associated with higher uptake than being less than 30 years.^{43,76}

Socioeconomic considerations including education level, employment status, and wealth index affect uptake of treatment. Being married was associated with higher uptake of IPTp-SP,^{11,26,43,76} Education level was reported on by many studies;^{8,10-12,21,25,26,28,32,35,38-40,42,43,45,46,60,76,77,79-81} higher education was generally associated with increased uptake, including in a large multi-country analysis of malaria indicator datasets.⁷⁷ On the contrary, analysis of the 2014 and 2017 malaria indicator surveys in Burkina Faso found that women with secondary or higher level of education were less likely than women with no education to receive adequate doses.¹³ A higher level of education among women's husbands (attainment of secondary education) was noted as a key predictor for optimal IPTp-SP uptake in one study in Nigeria.²⁶ Limited studies found a strong association between employment status and IPTp-SP uptake. One study found that women employed by the government had higher proportions of IPTp-SP uptake.¹¹ Two studies noted that employed women had a higher percentage of those who completed appropriate IPTp-SP doses versus women who were unemployed.^{7,80} With regards to wealth index, many studies reported that women in the 'middle' to 'richest' wealth index had higher uptake of IPTp-SP than those in the 'poorest' to 'poorer' wealth index; a large analysis of malaria indicator surveys from Burkina Faso, Ghana, Mali, Malawi, Kenya, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, and Uganda including 18,603 women found that women in the highest wealth quintile were more likely to receive at least 3 doses of IPTp-SP compared to the lower wealth quintiles.^{9,13,35,39,41,43,45,76,77,81,82}

Rural residence was inconsistently associated with improved IPTp-SP uptake. Studies conducted in Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, and Sierra Leone reported that women who lived in rural areas were more likely to take the recommended doses of IPTp-SP,^{13,32,59} while studies in Nigeria, Ghana, and Malawi reported that urban residence was associated with higher IPTp-SP uptake compared to rural.^{41,60,83} Living more than 5 km from the health facility was also associated with poorer uptake of IPTp-SP.²¹

Health system barriers, such as limited health coverage, were reported as influencers of IPTp-SP uptake.^{9,76} One study in Ghana found that women with health insurance coverage were much more likely to receive efficient doses of IPTp-SP.⁹ Another study Uganda had a similar finding, but with regards to health facility usage; women who were able to deliver inside of a covered/funded health facility were more likely to receive optimal doses of IPTp-SP.⁷⁶

Public messaging also plays a large role in influencing IPTp-SP uptake. Many studies reported that exposure to media messages (radio, internet, television, etc.) was associated with increased, optimal IPTp-SP uptake.^{9,41,42,77}

The tables below present an analysis of data from the most recent survey for each country available in StatCompiler (malaria indicator surveys and demographic health surveys) assessing coverage of at least three doses of IPTp-SP (IPTp3+) by education, residence, and wealth quintile. These data suggest that in some (but not all) countries, women with higher levels of education are more likely to receive at least 3 doses of IPTp-SP. Coverage in urban areas is slightly higher in most (but not all) countries, and

while a few countries have lower uptake in the lowest and second lowest wealth quintiles, this is generally equally distributed.

To the extent that IPTp-SP reaches those women at highest risk for adverse outcomes (including those living in more rural areas, farther from facilities, of lower socioeconomic status, and with less education), IPTp-SP reduces the risk of adverse health outcomes related to malaria. A number of studies suggest that distribution of SP is generally higher in women living in rural areas, which would be expected to improve health equity, however, there may be a gap in terms of reaching women living more than 5 km from health facilities (Rubenstein et al., pending publication), young women, and those of lower socioeconomic status and education.

Figure 1. Coverage of IPTp3+ by education level in sub-Saharan African countries using survey data from StatCompiler

Source: www.statcompiler.com Updated 2/3/2022

Figure 2. Coverage of IPTp3+ by residence (urban vs rural) in sub-Saharan African countries using survey data from StatCompiler

Source: www.statcompiler.com Updated 2/3/2022

Figure 3. Coverage of IPTp3+ by wealth quintile in sub-Saharan African countries using survey data from StatCompiler

Source: www.statcompiler.com Updated 2/3/2022

Conclusions

Overall, administering IPTp was found to be efficient and feasible, except for a few studies reporting IPTp-SP availability issues. In addition, four studies found that inadequate training and knowledge of health facility workers impacted delivery of IPTp-SP. While few studies specifically examined resource use amongst women receiving IPTp, some found that the lack of resource availability was a large contributor to accounts of low uptake. The use of DOT when administering IPTp-SP was found to be a critical component of efficient operations. Affordability was reported by a few studies as a major influence on resource use – many women had to pay out of pocket for ANC visits or IPTp. Addressing financial barriers for women to seek care is critical to ensure efficient uptake of IPTp-SP. IPTp-SP has been demonstrated to be highly cost effective, thus it behooves countries to ensure that women can access the recommended number of doses. Many studies reported the following sociodemographic factors as contributors to the issue of inequality of IPTp opportunity: age, marital status, religion, and urban/rural residence. Regarding equitable availability of IPTp, health system barriers and socioeconomic factors (education, employment, and wealth index) were reported as strong influencers of IPTp-SP uptake.

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Table 1. Studies included in the contextual factor summary

Study	Location	Study Year	Design	Contextual Factors[#]
Badirou 2018 ⁵	Cotonou, Benin	2015	cross sectional	A
Amankwah 2019 ²⁷	Tema, Ghana	2019*	cross sectional	A; F
Adewole 2019 ⁷	Oyo State, Nigeria	2015	cross sectional	A; F; HEq
Awantang 2018 ⁸	Madagascar	2014	cross sectional	A; HEq
Darteh 2020 ⁹	Ghana	2016	cross sectional, MIS	A; HEq
McHwampaka 2019 ¹⁰	Arusha region, Tanzania	2017	cross sectional	A; F; HEq
Tackie 2020 ¹¹	Winneba, Ghana	2019	cross sectional	A; HEq
Arnaldo 2018¹²	Chokwe district, Southern Mozambique	2014-2015	cross sectional	A; HEq
Bado 2021 ¹³	Burkina Faso	2014, 2017	cross sectional, MIS	A; HEq
Camara 2019 ¹⁴	Shai-Osudoku District, Ghana	2019	cross sectional	A
Gbenatey 2018 ¹⁵	Awutu Senya East Municipality, Ghana	2018*	cross sectional	A
Kamukama 2019 ¹⁶	Kabarole District, Uganda	2019	cross sectional	A; F
Lash 2019¹⁷	Geita Region, Tanzania	2019	cross sectional	A
Malpass 2020¹⁸	Ntcheu and Nkhata Bay Districts, Malawi	2017	cross sectional	A
Musasizi 2019 ¹⁹	Soroti district, Uganda	2014, 2016	cross sectional, MIS	A; F
Mutanyi 2021 ²⁰	Sabatia Sub County, Kenya	2020	cross sectional	A
Nkunzimana 2020 ²¹	Muramvya Health District, Burundi	2018	cross sectional	A; R; HEq
Oyerinde 2019 ²²	Ogun State, Nigeria	2016-2017	cross sectional	A
Sangho 2021 ²³	Selingue, Mali	2016	cross sectional	A
Vandy 2018 ⁴⁴	Keta District, Volta Region, Ghana	2018	cross sectional	A
Faye 2021 ⁴⁹	DRC; Nigeria; Mozambique	2018	qualitative (IDIs, FGDs, direct observation)	A; F
Patson 2020 ⁵⁰	Malawi	2020*	randomized trial	A
Amoako 2021 ²⁸	Cape Coast, Ghana	2018	cross sectional	A; HEq
Mafuleka 2018 ²⁵	Lilongwe, Malawi	2018	cross sectional	A; F; HEq
Akpa 2019 ²⁶	Ebonyi State, Nigeria	2019*	cross sectional	A; HEq
Anchang-Kimbi 2014 ²⁹	Mutengene, Cameroon	2007, 2008-2009	cross sectional	A
Anto 2019⁴⁶	Navrongo, Ghana	2017	cross sectional	A; HEq
Azizi 2020 ³⁰	Malawi	2015-2016	cross sectional, DHS	A
Babalola 2019 ³¹	Cote d'Ivoire	2018	cross sectional	A; F; HEq
Buh 2019 ⁸⁴	Sierra Leone	2016	cross sectional, MICS	A; HEq
Chinkhumba 2019 ³³	Malawi	2019*	cross sectional	A
De-Gaulle 2021 ³⁴	Volta Region, Ghana	2019	cross sectional	A; F
Diawara 2020 ³⁵	Mali	2015	cross sectional, MIS	A; HEq
Dosoo 2021³⁶	Dodowa, Kintampo, and Navrongo, Ghana	2017-2019	cohort	A

Dun-Dery 2021 ³⁷	Upper West Region, Ghana	2018-2019	mixed methods	A; F
Kissi 2018 ³⁸	Prestea Hunivalley District, Ghana	2018*	cross sectional	A; HEq
Muhammad 2020 ³⁹	Nigeria	2018	cross sectional, DHS cross sectional, DHS,	A; F; HEq
Mushi 2021 ⁴⁰	Tanzania	2015-2016	MIS	A; HEq
Ndu 2020 ⁴¹	Nigeria	2013	cross sectional, DHS	A; HEq
Okethwangu 2019 ⁴²	Uganda	2016	cross sectional, DHS	A; HEq
Olugbade 2019 ⁴³	Nigeria	2013	cross sectional, DHS	A; HEq
Yaya 2019 ⁴⁵	Ivory Coast	2016	cross sectional, MICS	A; HEq
Enguita 2020 ⁴⁷	DRC; Nigeria; Mozambique;	2018	cross sectional, IDIs, FGDs	A
Mbonye 2008 ⁸⁵	Madagascar	2008*	mixed methods	A
Zhou 2020 ⁵⁴	Mukono District, Uganda	2004, 2010, 2016	cross sectional	F
Aberese-Ako 2020 ⁵²	Western Kenya	2018-2019	ethnographic	F; R
Diengou 2020 ⁵¹	Ashanti and Volta regions, Ghana	2014	cross sectional	F
Peters 2020 ⁵³	Bamenda, Cameroon	2017	mixed methods	F; R
Vandy 2019 ²⁴	Abuja, Nigeria	2018	cross sectional	F
Marealle 2018 ⁵⁶	Volta Region, Ghana	2017	cross sectional	F
Yavo 2019 ⁵⁵	Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	2016	cross sectional	F
Hill 2020 ⁵⁸	Abidjan, Ivory Coast	2014, 2015	mixed methods	F
Toure 2014⁵⁹	Cote d'ivoire	2009-2010	cross sectional	F; R; HEq
Arnaldo 2019 ⁵⁷	Chokwe district, Southern Mozambique	2015	cross sectional, IDIs	F; R
Azizi 2018 ⁶⁰	Zomba district, Malawi	2016-2017	cross sectional	F; HEq
Nekaka 2020 ⁶¹	Mbale, Uganda	2017-2018	cross sectional	F
Ngapanya 2020 ⁶²	Dar es Salaam, Tanzania	2017	cross sectional	F
Onyebuchi 2014⁶³	Abakaliki, Nigeria	2012	cohort	F
Esu 2018 ⁸⁶	Southeast Nigeria	2013-2014	cross sectional	R
Bello 2019 ⁶⁵	Ibadan, Nigeria	2019*	cross sectional	R
Ejiogu 2019 ⁶⁶	Owerri, Nigeria	2019*	cross sectional	R
Owiti 2020 ⁶⁷	Kenya	2003, 2008- 2009, 2014	cross sectional, DHS	R
Walker 2017 ⁶⁸	Africa	2000-2015	Mathematical Model cross sectional, IDIs, FGDs	R; HEq
Muhammad 2021 ⁶⁹	Kano state, Nigeria	2021*	Mathematical Model	R
Fernandes 2015 ⁷⁰	Burkina Faso, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Tanzania, Zambia	2013	Mathematical Model	R
Menendez 2008⁷¹	Maputo Province, Mozambique	2002-2004	prospective, descriptive RCT, mathematical	R
Sicuri 2010 ⁷²	Maputo Province, Mozambique	2007-2008	model RCT, mathematical	R
Hansen 2012 ⁷³	Kabale District, Uganda	2004-2007	model	R
Onyia 2020 ⁷⁴	Nigeria	2018*	cross sectional	R

Addai-Mensah 2018 ⁷⁵	Kumasi, Ghana	2016	cross sectional	HEq
Martin 2020 ⁷⁶	East-Central Uganda	2016	cross sectional, DHS	HEq
Yaya 2018 ⁷⁷	Burkina Faso, Ghana, Mali, Malawi, Kenya, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Uganda	2014-2015	cross sectional, MIS	HEq
Oppong 2019 ⁷⁸	Kintampo, Ghana	2011-2015	Retrospective	HEq
Asiimwe 2019 ⁷⁹	Uganda	2016	cross sectional, DHS	HEq
Manirakiza 2011 ⁸⁰	Bangui, Central African Republic	2009	cross sectional	HEq
Pons-Duran 2020 ⁸¹	DRC, Madagascar, Mozambique, Nigeria	2020*	cross sectional	HEq
Okoli 2021 ⁸²	Nigeria	2018	cross sectional, DHS	HEq

A = acceptability, F = feasibility, R = resource use/ cost, HEq = health equity

*Study dates were not available, so date of publication is listed

Bolded studies were included in the quantitative synthesis

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References

1. World Health Organization. *World Malaria Report 2020*. 2020.
2. Hill J, Hoyt J, van Eijk AM, D'Mello-Guyett L, ter Kuile FO, et al. Factors Affecting the Delivery, Access, and Use of Interventions to Prevent Malaria in Pregnancy in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *PLoS Med*. 2013;10(7):e1001488. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1001488
3. World Health Organization. *World Malaria Report 2013*. 2013.
4. van Eijk AM, Larsen DA, Kayentao K, et al. Effect of Plasmodium falciparum sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance on the effectiveness of intermittent preventive therapy for malaria in pregnancy in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2019;19(5):546-556.
5. Badirou A, Georgia DB, Roméo PSG, Luc KM, Marius OE. Adherence to intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine and associated factors: A cross-sectional survey in benin's public hospitals. *Open Public Health Journal*. 2018;11:28-36. doi:10.2174/1874944501811010028
6. Amankwah S, Anto F. Factors Associated with Uptake of Intermittent Preventive Treatment of Malaria in Pregnancy: A Cross-Sectional Study in Private Health Facilities in Tema Metropolis, Ghana. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2019;2019 (no pagination)doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2019/9278432>
7. Adewole AO, Fawole O, Ajayi I, et al. Determinants of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria among women attending antenatal clinics in primary health care centers in Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria. *The Pan African medical journal*. 2019;33:101.
8. Awantang GN, Babalola SO, Koenker H, Fox KA, Toso M, Lewicky N. Malaria-related ideational factors and other correlates associated with intermittent preventive treatment among pregnant women in Madagascar. *Malaria Journal*. 2018;17(1):176.

9. Darteh EKM, Buabeng I, Akuamoah-Boateng C. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy for malaria: further analysis of the 2016 Ghana Malaria Indicator Survey. *Journal of Public Health*. 2020;
10. McHwampaka WM, Tarimo D, Chacky F, Mohamed A, Kishimba R, Samwel A. Factors affecting uptake of ≥ 3 doses of Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine for malaria prevention in pregnancy in selected health facilities, Arusha region, Tanzania. *BMC Pregnancy & Childbirth*. 2019;19(1):440.
11. Tackie V, Seidu AA, Osei M. Factors influencing the uptake of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria among pregnant women: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Public Health*. 2020;
12. Arnaldo P, Rovira-Vallbona E, Langa JS, et al. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment and pregnancy outcomes: health facilities and community surveys in Chokwe district, southern Mozambique. *Malaria Journal*. 2018;17(1):109.
13. Bado A, Badolo H, Hien MH, Lougué I, Appunni S, Méda N. Factors Associated with the Use of Intermittent Preventive Treatment (IPTp) by Women During Pregnancy in Burkina Faso. *World Journal of Public Health*. 6(3):110-120. doi:doi: 10.11648/j.wjph.20210603.15
14. Camara. *Low uptake of intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) for malaria among pregnant women in selected health facilities in Shai-Osudoku District, Greater Accra, Ghana*. 2019. <http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh/handle/123456789/34471>
15. Gbenatey. *Utilization of intermittent preventive treatment during pregnancy in the Awutu Senya East Municipality, a case study at the Kasoa Polyclinic*. 2018. <http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh/handle/123456789/26035>
16. Kamukama. *Factors associated with adherence to intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy among postnatal mothers at Fort Portal Regional Referral Hospital in Kabarole District*. 2019. <http://dSPACE.mak.ac.ug/handle/10570/7768>
17. Lash R, Lemwayi R, Assenga M, et al. Factors associated with achieving antenatal care (ANC) attendance and intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy (IPTp) recommendations in Geita Region, Tanzania, 2019. 74.
18. Malpass A, Chinkhumba J, Davlantes E, et al. Malaria knowledge and experiences with community health workers among recently pregnant women in Malawi. *Malaria Journal*. 2020;19(1):154.
19. Musasizi. *Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in pregnancy in Arapai sub county, Soroti district following a change in the drug administration policy*. 2019. <http://dSPACE.mak.ac.ug/handle/10570/8029>
20. Mutanyi JA, Onguru DO, Ogolla SO, Adipo LB. Determinants of the uptake of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy with sulphadoxine pyrimethamine in Sabatia Sub County, Western Kenya. *Infect Dis Poverty*. 2021;10(1):106. doi:10.1186/s40249-021-00887-4
21. Nkunzimana E, Babale M. Knowledge and utilization of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria among pregnant women in Muramvya Health District, Burundi, 2018. *East African Health Research Journal*. 2020;4(1):81-91. doi:10.24248/eahrj.v4i1.625
22. Oyerinde O, Adeyinka S, Kilanko A, et al. A study of compliance and clinics attendance among pregnant women intermittent preventive treatment of malaria during pregnancy, Ogun State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Social Sciences*. 2019;58(3):178-85.
23. Sangho O, Tounkara M, Whiting-Collins LJ, Beebe M, Winch PJ, Doumbia S. Determinants of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine in pregnant women (IPTp-SP) in Mali, a household survey. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):231. doi:10.1186/s12936-021-03764-5
24. Vandy AO, Peprah NY, Jerela JY, et al. Factors influencing adherence to the new intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy policy in Keta District of the Volta region, Ghana. *BMC Pregnancy & Childbirth*. 2019;19(1):424.
25. Mafuleka, Cheumchit. Factors influencing utilization of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria during pregnancy among mothers of under-one children in rural Lilongwe, Malawi. *Journal of Health Research*. 2018;32(Suppl 1):S62. doi:10.14456/jhr.2018.8

26. Akpa CO, Akinyemi JO, Umeokonkwo CD, et al. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in pregnancy among women in selected communities of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *BMC Pregnancy & Childbirth*. 2019;19(1):457.
27. Amankwah S, Anto F. Factors Associated with Uptake of Intermittent Preventive Treatment of Malaria in Pregnancy: A Cross-Sectional Study in Private Health Facilities in Tema Metropolis, Ghana. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2019;2019:9278432.
28. Amoako, B K, Anto. Late ANC initiation and factors associated with sub-optimal uptake of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine in pregnancy: a preliminary study in Cape Coast Metropolis, Ghana. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*. 2021;21(1):105. doi:10.1186/s12884-021-03582-2
29. Anchang-Kimbi JK, Achidi EA, Apinjoh TO, et al. Antenatal care visit attendance, intermittent preventive treatment during pregnancy (IPTp) and malaria parasitaemia at delivery. *Malaria Journal*. 2014;13(1)
30. Azizi, S C. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria during pregnancy with Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine in Malawi after adoption of updated World Health Organization policy: an analysis of demographic and health survey 2015-2016. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20(1):335. doi:10.1186/s12889-020-08471-5
31. Babalola S, Dosso A, Bleu MT, et al. Individual, household and community factors associated with the uptake of three doses of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy (IPTP3) in Cote D'ivoire: A multilevel analysis. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):122.
32. Buh A, Kota K, Bishwajit G, Yaya S. Prevalence and Associated Factors of Taking Intermittent Preventive Treatment in Pregnancy in Sierra Leone. *Tropical Medicine & Infectious Disease*. 2019;4(1):07.
33. Chinkhumba J, Malpass A, Wright K, et al. Timeliness of initiation of intermittent preventative treatment of malaria with sulfadoxinepyrimethamine (IPTP-SP) in pregnant women: Evidence from a cross sectional survey in Malawi. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):122-123.
34. De Galle V F, Magnussen, Tagbor. Assessing health system factors influencing the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in Ghana. 67.
35. Diawara S, I., Kayentao, Konate, et al. Coverage of malaria interventions during antenatal care in Mali. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*. 2020;30(2)doi:10.26717/BJSTR.2020.30.004938
36. Dosoo DK, Malm K, Oppong FB, et al. Effectiveness of intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP) in Ghana. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021;6(8)doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2021-005877
37. Dun-Dery F, Meissner P, Beiersmann C, et al. Uptake challenges of intermittent preventive malaria therapy among pregnant women and their health care providers in the Upper West Region of Ghana: A mixed-methods study. *Parasite Epidemiol Control*. 2021;15:e00222. doi:10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00222
38. Kissi A. *Factors associated with uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in pregnant women in Prestea Huni- Valley District in Western Region*. 2018.
<http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh/handle/123456789/26320>
39. Muhammad, F M, Majdzadeh, et al. Socioeconomic inequality in intermittent preventive treatment using sulphadoxine pyrimethamine among pregnant women in Nigeria. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20(1):1860. doi:10.1186/s12889-020-09967-w
40. Mushi V, Mbotwa CH, Zacharia A, Ambrose T, Moshi FV. Predictors for the uptake of optimal doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for intermittent preventive treatment of malaria during pregnancy in Tanzania: further analysis of the data of the 2015-2016 Tanzania demographic and health survey and malaria indicat. *Malaria Journal*. 2021;20(1)doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12936-021-03616-2>
41. Ndu A, Mbachu C, Anitube O, Ezeoke U. Inequities in the use of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine for malaria prophylaxis during pregnancy in Nigeria. *Malawi Medical Journal*. 2020;32(1):45-51.
42. Okethwangu D, Opigo J, Atugonza S, et al. Factors associated with uptake of optimal doses of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria among pregnant women in Uganda: analysis of data from the Uganda Demographic and Health Survey, 2016. *Malaria Journal*. 2019;18(1):250.

43. Olugbade OT, Ilesanmi OS, Gubio AB, Ajayi I, Nguku PM, Ajumobi O. Socio-demographic and regional disparities in utilization of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in pregnancy - Nigeria demographic health survey 2013. *The Pan African medical journal*. 2019;32(Suppl 1):13.
44. Vandy AON. *Factors influencing adherence to new intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy policy in Keta District in Volta Region, Ghana*. 2018.
<http://ugspace.ug.edu.gh/handle/123456789/26323>
45. Yaya S, Kota K, Buh A, Bishwajit G. Antenatal visits are positively associated with uptake of tetanus toxoid and intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy in Ivory Coast. *BMC Public Health*. 2019;19(1):1467.
46. Anto F, Agongo IH, Asoala V, Awini E, Oduro AR. Intermittent Preventive Treatment of Malaria in Pregnancy: Assessment of the Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine Three-Dose Policy on Birth Outcomes in Rural Northern Ghana. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2019;2019:6712685.
47. Enguita F, Alonso, Lusengi, et al. Trust, community health workers and delivery of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy: a comparative qualitative analysis of four sub-Saharan countries. *Global public health*. 2020:1-15. doi:10.1080/17441692.2020.1851742
48. Mbonye AK, Bygbjerg I, Magnussen P. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy: a community-based delivery system and its effect on parasitemia, anemia and low birth weight in Uganda. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2008;12(1):22-9.
49. Faye SLB, Lugand MM. Participatory research for the development of information, education and communication tools to promote intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Nigeria and Mozambique. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):223. doi:10.1186/s12936-021-03765-4
50. Patson, N P, Mukaka, et al. Role of adverse events on relationship between malaria chemoprevention during pregnancy and non-adherence; mediation analysis of a randomized trial. 75.
51. Diengou NH, Cumber SN, Nkfusai CN, et al. Factors associated with the uptake of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy in the Bamenda health districts, Cameroon. *The Pan African medical journal*. 2020;35:42.
52. Aberese-Ako M, Magnussen P, Gyapong M, Ampofo GD, Tagbor H. Managing intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy challenges: an ethnographic study of two Ghanaian administrative regions. *Malaria Journal*. 2020;19(1):347.
53. Peters GO, Naidoo M. Factors influencing the use of intermittent preventive treatment of pregnant women seeking care at primary healthcare facilities in the Bwari Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria. *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine*. 2020;12(1):e1-e8.
54. Zhou G, Hemming-Schroeder E, Gesuge M, et al. Gaps between Knowledge and Malaria Treatment Practices after Intensive Anti-Malaria Campaigns in Western Kenya: 2004-2016. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene*. 2020;102(6):1358-1365.
55. Yavo JC, Kouame R, Balayssac E, Assi SB, Kamagate M. Intermittent preventive treatment during pregnancy; assessment of prescription and compliance in 183 pregnant women in the Health Region of Abidjan 2 and their evolutions (2008/2016). *Fundamental and Clinical Pharmacology*. 2019;33 (Supplement 1):85.
56. Marealle AI, Mbwambo DP, Mikomangwa WP, Kilonzi M, Mlyuka HJ, Mutagonda RF. A decade since sulfonamide-based anti-malarial medicines were limited for intermittent preventive treatment of malaria among pregnant women in Tanzania. *Malaria Journal*. 2018;17(1):409.
57. Arnaldo P, Cambe MI, Magaco A, et al. Access to and use of preventive intermittent treatment for Malaria during pregnancy: A qualitative study in the Chokwe district, Southern Mozambique. *PLoS ONE [Electronic Resource]*. 2019;14(1):e0203740.
58. Hill J, Ouma P, Oluoch S, et al. Intermittent screening and treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy: implementation feasibility in a routine healthcare system setting in western Kenya. *Malaria Journal*. 2020;19(1):433.

59. Toure OA, Kone PL, Coulibaly MA, et al. Coverage and efficacy of intermittent preventive treatment with sulphadoxine pyrimethamine against malaria in pregnancy in Cote d'Ivoire five years after its implementation. *Parasites and Vectors*. 2014;7(1)
60. Azizi SC, Chongwe G, Chipukuma H, Jacobs C, Zgambo J, Michelo C. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria during pregnancy with Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP) among postpartum women in Zomba District, Malawi: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Pregnancy & Childbirth*. 2018;18(1):108.
61. Nekaka R, Nteziyaremye J, Oboth P, Iramiot JS, Wandabwa J. Malaria preventive practices and delivery outcomes: A cross-sectional study of parturient women in a tertiary hospital in Eastern Uganda. *PLoS ONE*. 2020;15 (8 August) (no pagination)(e0237407)
62. Ngapanya SA, Mikomangwa WP, Bwire GM, et al. Uptake of Intermittent Preventive Therapy Among Pregnant Women Living in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: a Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine*. 2020;2(4):408-413.
63. Onyebuchi AK, Lawani LO, Iyoke CA, Onoh CR, Okeke NE. Adherence to intermittent preventive treatment for malaria with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine and outcome of pregnancy among parturients in South East Nigeria. *Patient Preference and Adherence*. 2014;8:447-452.
64. Esu E, Tacoli C, Gai P, et al. Prevalence of the Pfdhfr and Pfdhps mutations among asymptomatic pregnant women in Southeast Nigeria. *Parasitology Research*. 2018;117(3):801-807.
65. Bello FA, Ayede AI. Prevalence of Malaria Parasitaemia and the Use of Malaria Prevention Measures in Pregnant Women in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Annals of Ibadan Postgraduate Medicine*. 2019;17(2):124-129.
66. Ejiogu IV, Okoro CI, Iyke-Ejiogu CM, Ihenetu F, Okoro OI. Evaluation of malaria parasitaemia and assessing the knowledge, attitude and practice of pregnant women attending health facilities in owerri metropolis towards malaria prevention and treatment. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):313.
67. Owiti E. Inequality of Opportunity in Prevention of Malaria in Pregnancy: The Case of Lake Victoria Region and Coastal Malaria Stable Areas in Kenya. *Value in Health*. 2020;23 (Supplement 1):S184.
68. Walker PGT, Floyd J, ter Kuile F, Cairns M. Estimated impact on birth weight of scaling up intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy given sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance in Africa: A mathematical model. *PLoS Medicine*. 2017;14(2)
69. Muhammad FM, Nedjat S, Sajadi HS, Parsaeian M, Assan A, Majdzadeh R. Malaria intermittent preventive treatment in Nigeria: a qualitative study to explore barriers. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2021;21(1):438. doi:10.1186/s12879-021-06135-2
70. Fernandes S, Sicuri E, Kayentao K, et al. Cost-effectiveness of two versus three or more doses of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria during pregnancy in sub-Saharan Africa: A modelling study of meta-analysis and cost data. *The Lancet Global Health*. 2015;3(3):e143-e153.
71. Menendez C, Bardaji A, Sigauque B, et al. A randomized placebo-controlled trial of intermittent preventive treatment in pregnant women in the context of insecticide treated nets delivered through the antenatal clinic. *PLoS ONE [Electronic Resource]*. 2008;3(4):e1934.
72. Sicuri E, Bardaji A, Nhampossa T, et al. Cost-effectiveness of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy in southern Mozambique. *PLoS ONE [Electronic Resource]*. 2010;5(10):e13407.
73. Hansen KS, Ndyomugenyi R, Magnussen P, Clarke SE. Cost-effectiveness analysis of three health interventions to prevent malaria in pregnancy in an area of low transmission in Uganda. *International Health*. 2012;4(1):38-46.
74. Onyia VU, Ughasoro MD, Onwujekwe OE. The economic burden of malaria in pregnancy: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Maternal-Fetal and Neonatal Medicine*. 2020;33(1):92-95. doi:10.1080/14767058.2018.1487933
75. Addai-Mensah O, Annani-Akollor ME, Fondjo LA, et al. Regular Antenatal Attendance and Education Influence the Uptake of Intermittent Preventive Treatment of Malaria in Pregnancy: A Cross-Sectional Study at the University Hospital, Kumasi, Ghana. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2018;2018:5019215.

76. Martin MK, Venantius KB, Patricia N, et al. Correlates of uptake of optimal doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for prevention of malaria during pregnancy in East-Central Uganda. *Malaria Journal*. 2020;19(1):153.
77. Yaya S, Uthman OA, Amouzou A, Bishwajit G. Use of Intermittent Preventive Treatment among Pregnant Women in Sub-Saharan Africa: Evidence from Malaria Indicator Surveys. *Tropical Medicine & Infectious Disease*. 2018;3(1):11.
78. Oppong FB, Gyaase S, Zandoh C, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment of pregnant women in Kintampo area of Ghana with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP): trends spanning 2011 and 2015. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(6):e027946.
79. Asimwe. *Determinants of optimal uptake of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria during pregnancy in Uganda*. 2019. <http://hdl.handle.net/10570/7694>
80. Manirakiza A, Serdouma E, Djalle D, et al. Relatively low prevalence of peripheral and placental plasmodium infection at delivery in Bangui, Central African Republic. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2011;(no pagination)
81. Pons-Duran C, Llach M, Sacoar C, et al. Coverage of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy in four sub-Saharan countries: findings from household surveys. *International journal of epidemiology*. 2020;08doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyaa233>
82. Okoli CI, Hajizadeh M, Rahman MM, Khanam R. Decomposition of socioeconomic inequalities in the uptake of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy in Nigeria: evidence from Demographic Health Survey. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):300. doi:10.1186/s12936-021-03834-8
83. Oppong FB, Gyaase S, Anane EA, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment with sulphadoxine pyrimethamine (SP) among pregnant women in Kintampo area of Ghana - Findings from 2011 to 2015. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):123.
84. Bah, E M, Balde, et al. Congenital malaria and pregnancy monitoring parameters in health facilities in Guinea. *Open Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2019;9:73-82. doi:10.4236/ojog.2019.91008
85. Mbonye AK, Schultz Hansen K, Bygbjerg IC, Magnussen P. Effect of a community-based delivery of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in pregnancy on treatment seeking for malaria at health units in Uganda. *Public Health*. 2008;122(5):516-525.
86. Esu E, Berens-Riha N, Pritsch M, Nwachuku N, Loescher T, Meremikwu M. Intermittent screening and treatment with artemether-lumefantrine versus intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for malaria in pregnancy: a facility-based, open-label, non-inferiority trial in Nigeria. *Malaria Journal*. 2018;17(1):251.